

THE HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF WEIGHTLIFTING IN THE WORLD

Ismailov Makhmudbek Nodirbek uglu

Student of Urgench State University

E-mail: ismailovmahmudjon@bk.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6965448>

Abstract: In this thesis, the origin and development of the sport of weightlifting, the participants in the first Olympic Games and the achieved results are sufficiently discussed.

Key words: Weightlifting, sport, strength, weight, methodology.

Among the various means and methods of physical education, weight classes have a special place. They have been known since ancient times. People have long noticed that physical work with weights strengthens the muscles, makes the joints more mobile and the body more resistant. There is no doubt that one of the oldest of all sports is weightlifting. This sport is as natural as walking, running, wrestling. As mentioned earlier, even trees need movement to be strong and durable. A strong man, even if he is healthy, should train with heavy objects every day and develop muscles. Humanity understood this thousands of years ago, and people who wanted to be strong trained with different weights.

At the beginning of the 13th century BC, weightlifting began to develop rapidly. is celebrated in the form of Thus, we can say with great truth that the homeland of weightlifting is ancient Greece, where the worship of body beauty and physical perfection rose to unprecedented heights. Sports equipment made of stone or metal connected by handles is considered the prototype of modern dumbbells and barbells. It is also known that on the square in Athens there is a weighty core that any Greek can try to lift to test himself, to show his strength to his countrymen. However, there is a lot of beautiful fantasy about the strength and dexterity of the ancient Greek Olympians that has come down to our time and in the data.

As the ancient Greek philosopher Plato said, "A person who combines strength, health and endurance, strong will, intelligence and high culture is a real weightlifter." There is no person who does not want to achieve sufficient strength and a beautiful figure. For this purpose, a simple barbell serves as the main sports equipment. The word "barbell" is derived from the German language stange, which means an iron rod (in modern terms, a griffin). The weightlifting barbell has been modified several times to date. There is no doubt that weightlifting is the oldest of all sports. It has a long history of running, javelin throwing, and wrestling. From ancient times, people competed to test

their strength, compete in agility and endurance. Of course, athletic performances were held during the holidays. The conditions of the competition were determined on the spot, in the circle of the competitors, in front of the eyes of the people. The equipment of the competition was a sack of wheat, and another served as a blacksmith's sandal or a kharsangstone projectile. An object of desired weight was used as a measure of physical strength.

We can consider Milo Kratonsky, student of the famous scientist Pythagoras, who lived in the 6th century BC, as the first weightlifter. Unlike the legendary Greek Hercules, Milon Kratonsky had great muscular strength. He achieved this through relentless training. Kratonsky practiced lifting boulders and carrying heavy loads, and in his youth carried a calf on his shoulders. The calf is growing up. first he turned into a bull, and then into a heavy bull, but Milon carried him on his shoulders every day. According to Pavzani's testimony, Milon was able to carry a four-year-old bull on his shoulders and run across the entire field. Legends about his strength and passion have come down to us. Kratonsky's compatriot, the sculptor Darnkas, made a bronze statue of Milo. The statue was heavy in appearance, and the ancient Greek historian Pavzanius, counting the bravery of the wrestler, wrote: "Milan was so powerful that he could freely hold his statue on his shoulders."

In addition to Great Britain, athletics began to develop widely in the south of France, Italy, Germany, Austria, and the Netherlands. In 1860, weightlifting began to take shape as a sport. In many European countries, the USA, Canada, Australia, weightlifting clubs and training clubs began to open and competition rules appeared. Tournaments for athletes were held there. Due to this, weightlifting was included in the program of the 1st Olympic Games held in Athens in the summer of 1896. Two years later, the first official World Championship was held in Venice.

In 1896, before the Olympic Games, strong teams from Holland, Austria, Denmark, France and Germany gathered and held the first European Championship. At that time, athletes were not divided into weight categories. At the same time, everyone showed what they are capable of. At that time, Bavarian brewer Hans Beck was recognized as the strongest. He managed to deadlift 130 kg, deadlift and press 135 kg with two hands. The achievements of the first Olympians turned out to be much simpler, because for some reason the strongest athletes did not participate in the competition. Denmark's Viggo Jensen won the Olympic gold medal in Athens lifting 111.5 kg.

It is difficult to determine when and where weightlifting became a sports discipline. The birth history of weightlifting is closely related to other types of sports, namely wrestling, boxing, rowing, athletics. In the last 10 years of the 19th century and the first half of the 20th century, weightlifting began to take shape as a modern sport.

References:

1. Matkarimov.R.M. Theory and methodology of weightlifting: a textbook for physical education institutions. T.: 2015
2. Dvorkin L.S. Weightlifting: a textbook for universities. Moscow: Soviet sport, 2005. - 600 p.
3. Matkarimov R.M. Weightlifters have many years of training scientific and theoretical foundations of the system: Monograph. T.:2021.

